

APPLICATION OF THE LEBESGUE INTEGRAL AND MEASURE THEORY IN MATHEMATICAL MODELING

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Abstract. *This article provides an overview of the fundamentals of the Lebesgue integral and measure theory, and their applications in mathematical modeling, probability theory, and various mathematical problems. It discusses the differences between the traditional Riemann integral and the Lebesgue integral, the concept of Lebesgue measure, and the role of sigma-algebras. Practical examples illustrate the advantages and unique characteristics of these methods.*

Keywords: *lebesgue integral, measure theory, sigma-algebra, measurable function, probability theory, integration methods, mathematical model, function measurement.*

Introduction

Integral theory is a fundamental part of mathematics and has been widely used in many fields for decades. It is possible to calculate a field of continuous functions using the traditional Riemann integral, but this method does not provide complete solutions for some types of functions. In particular, the Riemann integral cannot be used to integrate functions with discrete changes or discontinuities at certain points. The Lebesgue integral and measure theory play an important role in solving these problems and allow us to integrate a wider class of functions.

The Lebesgue integral is more general than the Riemann integral because it integrates a function over a set of values. In this method, the "values" of the set are measured and integrated over the result of the measurement. Therefore, the Lebesgue integral can be used to integrate discontinuous functions, that is, functions whose values change abruptly at certain points. These variable, discontinuous functions are common in probability theory, statistical analysis, physics, and other applied mathematical fields, and it is important to ensure their further integration.

The ability to integrate discrete and continuous functions using the Lebesgue integral is based on the basic principles of measure theory. One of the main tools of measure theory is the sigma algebra, which helps define a measure and provides the necessary structure for calculating the Lebesgue integral. Thanks to the concept of sigma algebra and related measurement methods, the Lebesgue integral not only allows for traditional field calculations, but is also used in the analysis of probability distributions and the measurement of many types of functions.

Therefore, the purpose of this article is to provide a general overview of the theoretical foundations of the Lebesgue integral and measure theory, as well as their practical applications. The main focus is on the differences between the Lebesgue and Riemann integrals, the importance of the Lebesgue measure, and the role of the sigma algebra in the process of calculating the integral. These integration methods are of great importance in modern mathematical research and scientific modeling. The article also shows, through examples, the calculation of integrals of complex and variable functions using the Lebesgue integral.

Methods Section

Sigma algebra is a set of sets that is used to define the concept of measure. A sigma algebra satisfies the following conditions:

1. The empty set belongs to the sigma algebra.
2. If A is included in the sigma algebra, then the complement of A is also included in the sigma algebra.
3. If the sigma algebra contains successive sets A1, A2, ... An, then their combination is also included in the sigma algebra.

Sigma algebra is used to introduce the concept of measurement and is based on the Lebesgue integral.

Measure is a given function for sets included in the sigma algebra, which must satisfy several important conditions:

1. The dimension of the empty set is zero: $m(\emptyset) = 0$.
2. If sets are connected without intersecting each other, then their common measure is equal to the sum of the measures of each set:

$$m\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i\right) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} m(A_i)$$

The concept of measure plays an important role in the definition of the Lebesgue integral. By measuring, we can measure the space of functions more precisely.

Lebesgue Integral

The Lebesgue integral is a method of integrating a function by measuring. Unlike the Riemann integral, the Lebesgue integral is based on a set of function values.

The function $h(x)$ is defined as:

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} 2x, & 0 \leq x < 1 \\ x + 3, & 1 \leq x \leq 2 \\ 0, & x > 2 \end{cases}$$

Let's integrate this function on the interval $[0, 3]$ using the Lebesgue integral.

Solution:

The function is defined on three intervals, so we calculate the Lebesgue integral for each interval separately and add them up.

In the interval $[0, 1)$: $h(x) = 2x$.

$$\int_{[0,1)} h(x)dx = \int_0^1 2x dx = [x^2]_0^1 = 1^2 - 0^2 = 1$$

In the interval $[1, 2]$: $h(x) = x + 3$.

$$\int_{[2,3]} h(x)dx = \int_1^2 (x + 3)dx = \left[\frac{x^2}{2} + 3x\right]_1^2 = 8 - 3.5 = 4.5$$

In the interval $[2, 3]$: $h(x) = 0$.

$$\int_{[0,1)} h(x)dx = 0$$

Total Lebesgue integral:

$$\int_{[0,3)} h(x)dx = 1 + 4.5 + 0 = 5.5$$

Thus, the value of the Lebesgue integral of $h(x)$ on the interval $[0, 3]$ is 5.5.

Integrating a function with discrete and continuous parts

We measure the following function using the Lebesgue integral. This function has discrete and continuous values in different parts and is considered as an example of a probability model. The function $f(x)$ is given by:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 4, & x \in \{1, 3, 5, 7\}, \\ \frac{1}{x}, & x \in [1, 4], \\ 0, & \text{boshqa holatlar.} \end{cases}$$

Here the values of $f(x)$ are defined in two different cases:

The discrete values are $f(x) = 4$ at the points $x = 1, 3, 5, 7$.

$x \in [1, 4]$ is the continuous part such that $f(x) = 1/x$.

Objective: Calculate the Lebesgue integral of a function on the interval $[0, 5]$.

Solution: When calculating the Lebesgue integral, we measure the discrete and continuous parts of the function separately and then sum the results.

1. Integration of discrete parts

The discrete values are defined at the points $x = 1, 3, 5, 7$ and are $f(x) = 4$. According to the Lebesgue integral, the measure of the points is the sum of the area of the discrete values.

$$\int_{\{1,3,5,7\}} f(x)dx = \sum_{x \in \{1,3,5,7\}} f(x) \cdot m(\{x\}) = 4 \cdot 4 = 16.$$

where $m(\{x\})$ is taken as 1 as the measure of each point.

2. Integrating the Continuous Part

Now we measure the interval $[1, 4]$ where $f(x) = 1/x$.

$$\int_{[1,4]} f(x)dx = \int_1^4 \frac{1}{x} dx$$

We calculate this integral:

$$\int_1^4 \frac{1}{x} dx =]\ln |x|]_1^4 = \ln 4 - \ln 1 = \ln 4 = 2\ln 2.$$

3. Generalization of Results

Now we add the results obtained from the discrete and continuous parts:

$$\int_{[0,5]} f(x)dx = 16 + 2\ln 2.$$

Final Answer.

Thus, the Lebesgue integral of the function $f(x)$ on the interval $[0, 5]$ is equal to:

$$\int_{[0,5]} f(x)dx = 16 + 2\ln 2.$$

This solution shows how complex functions can be calculated in a mathematical model by integrating the discrete and continuous parts using the Lebesgue integral.

Measurement Functions

Integrating mathematical models using the Lebesgue integral and measure theory provides a wider range of possibilities. For example, probability theory uses Lebesgue integrals to calculate probabilities using various probability distributions.

The Lebesgue integral and measure theory are widely used in various areas of mathematical modeling, including probability theory, statistical analysis, economic models, and signal processing. Using the Lebesgue integral, continuous or discrete probability distributions can be analyzed, which allows for accurate results in the process of statistical models and probability calculations.

In measurement theory, the concept of sigma algebras and the definition of measurement through them are of great importance. Using sigma algebras, sets and their measure can be defined, which serves as the mathematical basis for the Lebesgue integral. For example, in probability theory, probability distributions are defined by measurements based on sigma algebras, and probability density functions are calculated using integrals. This process allows us to accurately measure probability masses and visualize probabilities as fields.

The Lebesgue integral measurement method allows us not only to calculate the areas of sets, but also to divide probability density functions or other complex functions into parts and integrate each part separately. With this method, analyzing complex mathematical models into simple parts is very effective, especially when working with continuous and discontinuous functions.

Results Section

Using the Lebesgue integral and measure theory, it is possible to integrate complex functions in mathematical models, which, unlike the Riemann integral, is also applicable to non-continuous functions. Discrete and discontinuous functions are also easier to measure.

Integrating complex functions using the Lebesgue integral and measure theory opens up new possibilities in mathematical modeling. This method covers a much wider class of functions compared to the Riemann integral and allows for the exact calculation of discrete or abruptly changing functions. Thus, probability density functions, signals with discontinuities, and distribution functions with discontinuities can be defined and integrated. The Lebesgue integral calculates the total area and measure of discrete and discontinuous functions, which can be used in various probability theory and statistical analysis. In addition, this method can be widely used in the analysis of complex economic models and signals, as well as in such areas as optimal control theory. Therefore, the method of measuring functions using the Lebesgue integral and measure theory is of great importance for modern mathematical models and practical analysis.

Discussion section

The Lebesgue integral and measure theory occupy an important place in modern mathematical models and probability theory. For example, it is possible to determine the probabilities of various sets using the measure-theoretic approach to probability. This theory is now widely used in statistics, quantum mechanics and other sciences. The Lebesgue integral is also important in solving various problems of a mathematical model.

The importance of the Lebesgue integral and measure theory is that they allow solving problems of mathematical modeling and probability theory that cannot be solved using the traditional Riemann integral. For example, accurate results can be obtained by measuring and integrating functions with continuous or discrete variables.

In quantum mechanics, the Lebesgue integral is used to define complex concepts such as quantum states and probability density. In statistics, probability density functions based on measure theory help to model and analyze complex distributions. Also, in optimal control and

financial analysis, mathematical models built on the Lebesgue integral are used to find solutions to such problems as investment management, risk assessment, and signal processing.

Therefore, the Lebesgue integral and measure theory are universal tools of modern scientific and practical analysis and are widely used in various fields of science.

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